

CLASSIFICATION OF TOURIST CLUSTERS AND PRINCIPLES
OF SUCCESSFUL OPERATION

Musulmonova Sh, Fatilloev F.

Musulmonova Shahlo - teacher

Fatilloev Farrux – student

Department of Economy

Bukhara State University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Abstract. *In the modern economy, the relations between economic subjects are not limited to the contracts concluded in the middle or the vertical relations of the internal enterprise. State intervention in management, i.e. participation in coordinating economic activities based on the interests of the people, is called economic quasi-integration. Currently, a "cluster" is accepted as a type of quasi-integration in developed countries, which means a collection of enterprises performing various economic activities. Despite the fact that touristic clusters are theoretically similar structures with common and unique aspects, in practice, the question of their scientific classification remains open.*

Key words: *cluster, "Hub-and-spoke" clusters, production and national clusters, entrepreneurial structures.*

In world practice, the general classification of cluster structures proposed by the German researcher Georg Mayer-Stamer in the 90s of the XX century can be applied to the field of tourism.

The first form of these clusters, i.e. clusters based on small and medium-sized businesses, is mainly known in foreign literature as the "Italian model" and was first applied to the industrial regions of this country. In clusters of this category, highly specialized small and medium-sized enterprises play a key role in

order to maximally satisfy the requirements for the quality and quantity of economic benefits produced within this structure. The internal network nature of the cluster structure is ensured by the high level of cooperative relations and speed of interaction between market entities. At the same time, the cluster system itself is distinguished by its high level of flexibility, which allows to respond quickly enough to changes in the market situation at the local and regional level, as well as at the international level.

"Hub-and-spoke" clusters play the role of a socio-economic platform where there is an opportunity for mutually beneficial cooperation of large, including transnational corporations and network associations with small and medium-sized businesses in a certain area. These clusters also operate without losing the flexibility of business processes due to increased competitive advantages.

Satellite clusters are characterized by a high share of small and medium-sized businesses in the cluster dependent on external organizations. This leads to a decrease in the efficiency of conducting joint commercial activities and non-rational use of the limited economic resources available at the disposal. As an example in the field of tourism, clusters with business tourism as their core can be mentioned.

As a result of studying cluster experience in many countries, I.V. Pilipenko distinguishes its network and regional forms:

- network clusters - interrelated groups of subjects of agricultural, production and service sectors successfully specializing in international division of labor (production and national clusters);
- regional clusters - production of similar or complementary products located geographically densely in a certain area, and due to the establishment of information exchange between cluster members, maintaining competitiveness at the international level. group of interconnected enterprises (regional, cross-border and local clusters).

Cluster policy is a set of measures aimed at increasing the country's competitiveness by encouraging the development of clusters. 4 types are distinguished depending on the role of the state in the implementation of the cluster policy

1. Catalytic - the manifestation of the state as a "catalyst" in the joint action of mutually interested parties, for example, private companies and scientific research organizations, through limited financing of projects.

2. Supportive - in addition to the catalytic cluster policy of state authorities, a complex of significant investments in regional infrastructure, improvement of higher, secondary and post-secondary education stages, and stimulation of cluster development performs actions such as measures.

3. Directive (instructive) - development of clusters aimed at changing the specialization of regions through the development and implementation of special programs by the state due to the expansion of the supporting cluster policy

4. Interventionist - while the state carries out directive cluster policy, it assumes responsibility and decision-making regarding the development prospects of clusters by transferring specialization of the private sector, subsidizing, placing legal barriers, and exercising control over the enterprises forming the cluster.

M. Enright researched 160 regional clusters and found that in 40% of them, cluster policy supported by state management bodies, catalytic cluster policy in 20%, directive cluster policy in 5% and intervention cluster policy was implemented in 2-3% of cases.

The implementation of the cluster approach in the tourism industry has several difficulties, including: the lack of experience in this field, the lack of methodological developments in the field of formation and management of tourist clusters, the lack of qualified specialists in the management of tourist clusters.

Tourist cluster means a set of business structures, authorities and state agencies, public organizations that operate in the tourism industry and in

intermediate sectors, and jointly use the tourist resources of a certain region in order to meet tourist needs and increase the competitiveness of the regional economy.

The main characteristics of tourist clusters are shown in the following:

- ✓ the existence of cooperation between tourism cluster subjects operating in the tourism industry and intermediate sectors (public and private sector partnership, union, association, etc.) (entrepreneurial structures, authorities and state agencies, public organizations);
- ✓ joint use of the tourist resources of the area with tourist attractions and tourist infrastructure by tourist cluster entities;
- ✓ existence of vertical (within the product chain of the tourism industry) and horizontal (among structures involved in the production of tourism products) interactions among the participants of the tourism cluster;
- ✓ the existence of a single goal of the operation of the touristic cluster, that is, to increase the competitiveness of the objects and subjects of the cluster, and to satisfy the recreational needs due to the formation, promotion and realization of the touristic product of the region.

The main principles of the tourist cluster:

- 1) mutual understanding of all process participants and readiness for cooperation;
- 2) equal rights of constructive dialogue participants;
- 3) freedom in choosing the form of cooperation;
- 4) fulfillment of obligations and mutual notification according to business contracts concluded between cluster participants.

The essence of the interaction between its members in a tourist cluster is that the good performance of one of them is a guarantee of the success of the other participants and represents a mutual collective market.

As a result of the study of the world experience of regional touristic clusters, the principles of successful functioning of clusters were formed:

The principle of sustainability: sustainable development at the expense of tourism product diversification

The principle of uniformity: relying on the uniqueness of local traditions, history and regional resources

The principle of synergy is the integration of cluster participants on the basis of partnership relations, interaction and functional integrity.

The principle of innovation is a creative approach to the presentation of tourism products that enhances the interaction of consumers, producers and society.

The principle of informatization: Wide use of information and communication technologies for the purpose of tourism development

The principle of state participation: State support for tourism development, state and private sector partnership in the implementation of innovation projects

The principle of integrity is a system of comprehensive management, unity of strategic goals and tactical tasks

References

1. Shahlo, M., & Aziza, T. (2023). External Labor Migration And Informal Employment: Situation, Problems And Their Causes. *European Journal Of Business Startups And Open Society*, 3(12), 45-50.
2. Gulchehra, N. (2023). The Role Of Creative Marketing In Creating Modern Brands. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Vuxdu. Uz)*, 34(34).
3. Muhammedrizayevna, T. M., O'tkir, Q. M., Djumanazarovna, X. G., & Bayazovna, G. N. (2020). Ensuring Sustainable Development Of Tourism Through The Formation Of Tourism Clusters. *International Journal Of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(6), 3893-3899.

4. Sh, A. F., & Aminova, N. B. (2022). Logistics In Strategic Planning Of Tourist Activities. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 215-219.

5. Sayfullayeva, M. (2023). Digitalisation And Sustainable Tourism: Enhanced Benefits. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Вухду. Уз)*, 35(35).

6. Akhrorovna, B. M. (2023). Budget-Tax Policy As A Means Of State Regulation Of The Market Economy. *Imras*, 6(6), 249-253.

7. Abdulloev, A. J. (2020). China's Experience In Organizing Cooperations In Farms. *Scientific Reports Of Bukhara State University*, 3(1), 247-252.

8. Bakhadirovna, U. A., & Hasanovna, A. D. (2022). The Role Of The State In Increasing Tourism Opportunities. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(12), 175-178.

9. Navruz-Zoda, Z. (2023). As A Tool For Promoting Area Marketing To Customers. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Вухду. Уз)*, 30(30).

10. Junaydulloyevich, A. A., Bakhridinovna, A. N., & Rasul-Kizi, K. D. (2022). Ways To Improve The Logistics Approach In Tourism. *Gospodarka I Innowacje.*, 24, 577-581.

11. Kayimova, Z. A., & Bakayeva, M. A. (2022). The Role Of Islamic Finance In The Capital Market In Uzbekistan. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 370-373.

12. Hakimovna, U. M., & Muhammedrisaevna, T. M. S. (2022). The Role Of Banking And Accounting In The Development Of Small Business And Entrepreneurship. *International Journal Of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research Issn: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429*, 11, 136-143.

13. Abdullajanova, D. S. (2023). Socio-Psychological Criteria For The Selection And Placement Of Personnel In Management (On The Example Of Women). *Confrencea*, 5(05), 401-411.

14. Abdullayevna, Q. Z., Anvarovich, Q. A., & Muxtorovna, N. D. Theoretical Foundations Of Enhancing The Competitiveness Of The National Economy. *Gwalior Management Academy*, 87, 54.

15. Jamshedovna, K. H. (2022). The Role Of Corporate Governance In Bank Management. *European Journal Of Business Startups And Open Society*, 2(11), 32-36.

16. Muhammedrisaevna, T. M., & Kahramanovna, D. A. (2022). Logistic Tourism System: Features, Functions And Opportunities. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 198-200.

17. Rustamovich, K. M. (2023). The Impact Of Using Key Performance Indicators On The Development Of Higher Education Institutions. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal Of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 385-390.

18. Igamova, S. (2022). Features Of Innovation At Industry Of Building Materials Enterprises. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 24(24).

19. Anvar O'g'li, Q. O. (2022). The Economic Modernization Of Uzbekistan. *Pedagogs Jurnal*, 23(1), 45-53.

20. Niyozova, I. (2021). The Transition To The Green Economy And The Importance Of Strategy. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 8(8).

21. Narzullayeva, G. S., & Bakayeva, M. A. (2022). Creative Management: Creative Opportunities In Business Process Management. *American Journal Of Social And Humanitarian Research*, 3(12), 58-63.

22. Giyazova, N. B., & Zayniev, A. A. (2020). Types Of Marketing Communications And Their Classification. In *International Scientific Review Of The Problems Of Economics, Finance And Management* (Pp. 32-38).

23. Yunusovna, N. K., & Gafurova, S. K. (2020). Modern Approaches To The Management Of The Quality Of Educational Services In Higher Educational

Institutions And The System Of Use Of Pedagogical Technologies. *International Journal Of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(6), 9229-9234.

24. Shahlo, M., & Aziza, T. (2023). Poverty As A Socio-Economic Category. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 3(12), 27-31.

25. Усманова, А. (2023). Analysis Of Methods For Assessing The Volume Of The Region's Tourism Potential. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Vixdi. Uz)*, 27(27).

